

STATE OF DISCRIMINATION

Legal barriers on women's right to choose work in India

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Executive Summary

India’s Female Labour Force Participation rate (FLFPR) is key to unlocking economic growth. Reforming labour regulations is a critical requirement for ensuring women’s economic empowerment. In 2022, State of Discrimination Report found that there are over 250+ laws that discriminate against female job seekers in India.

This update to the State of Discrimination Report presents the change in legally-sanctioned discrimination against female job seekers since 2022. 23 states are assessed on the preponderance of four restrictions on female job seekers: (1) working at night; (2) working in jobs deemed hazardous; (3) working in jobs deemed arduous; and (4) working in jobs deemed morally inappropriate. Each state is scored on a scale of 0 to 100 based on four broad categories. The answer to the question ‘can women do X?’ could be ‘no’, ‘yes, subject to permission’, ‘yes, subject to conditions’, and ‘yes’. For the complete methodology, refer to the State of Discrimination Report 2023. All the datasets from the report are available on our GitHub.

Table 1: State Rankings on the SoD Index

State	2024	2022
Goa	1	3
Kerala	2	1
Jharkhand	3	8
Himachal Pradesh	4	4
Tamil Nadu	5	2
Karnataka	6	5
Rajasthan	7	7
Maharashtra	8	8
Uttar Pradesh	9	10
Telangana	10	16
Andhra Pradesh	11	12
Uttarakhand	12	19
Bihar	13	6
Madhya Pradesh	14	22
Odisha	15	23
Chhattisgarh	16	20
Haryana	17	14
Punjab	17	14
Tripura	19	18
West Bengal	20	20
Assam	21	17

What was the state of discrimination against female job seekers in India in 2024?

- Goa, Kerala, and Jharkhand provide the greatest freedom for women to choose work.
- Tripura, West Bengal, and Assam impose the most restrictions on women's employment.
- Jharkhand has jumped five spots to improve its ranking from 8 in 2022 to 3 in 2024. Similarly, Telangana has improved its ranking from 16 in 2022 to 10 in 2024.
- Tamil Nadu has dropped 3 places, from rank 2 in 2022 to rank 5 in 2024. Bihar dropped from rank 6 in 2022 to 13 in 2024.
- States give the least freedom on the employment of women in jobs deemed arduous. This indicator has an average score of 2.91 out of 100.
- The second lowest performance across states is on the employment of women in factories at night. The average score on this indicator is 39.79.
- States impose the least restrictions on women in jobs deemed hazardous in shops and commercial establishments. The average score on this indicator is 93.70.
- The indicator, 'can women work in licensed country liquor establishments,' records the greatest inter-state variation in scores (standard deviation of 43.8). There is no variation on the indicator 'can women work in plantations at night', as it is prohibited across all states.
- The Factories Act, 1948, contains the most restrictions of all the laws studied, including on the employment of women at night, the employment of women in jobs deemed hazardous, and the employment of women in jobs deemed arduous.

How did indicators of female labour force participation relate to the state of discrimination in 2024?

- The average female unemployment rate is 10.39% across states that have above-median ratings, compared to 12.36% in states with below-median ratings.
- The average female labour force participation rate is 38.18% in states that have above-median ratings, compared to 36.09% in states with below-median ratings.
- On average, there are 210 women in managerial positions per 1,000 persons in states with above-median ratings. In states with ratings below median, there are 197 women in managerial positions per 1,000 persons.
- On average, women's salaries are 77.4% of men's salaries in the states with above-median ratings, compared to 67.7% in states with below-median ratings.
- The Sustainable Development Goal 5 (gender equality and women's empowerment) index scores and State of Discrimination Report ratings are positively correlated ($r = 0.44$).

How free were India's female job seekers in 2022 and 2024?

2022

- The employment of women at night was the most heavily legislated subject.
- Most restrictions were in the Factories Act, 1948.
- States gave the least freedom to women in jobs deemed arduous.
- States imposed the most restrictions on women in job deemed hazardous in shops and commercial establishments.
- Kerala was the most free state and Odisha was the least free state.

2024

- Most changes were made to women working at night in factories (7 states).
- Most changes were made by Telangana (2).
- Three states (Jharkhand, Odisha, and Telangana) have improved their scores on women's freedom to work.
- Women working at night continues to be the most heavily regulated subject.
- Goa has emerged as the most free state while Meghalaya is the least free state.

Figure 1: State rankings on the SoD Index, 2022

Figure 2: State rankings on the SoD Index, 2024

Detailed findings from 2024

Indicator 1 (P111): Can women work at night in factories?

Since 2022, seven states have eased restrictions on women working at night in factories.

- Of 23 states, 3 continue to prevent women from working at night in factories.
- Of 23 states, 4 allow women to work at night in only a few industries, based either on conditions (2/23) or permissions (2/23).
- Of 23 states, 16 now allow women to work at night in factories, subject to either conditions (13/23) or permission (3/23) in all industries.

Figure 1: Women’s freedom to work at night in factories

*Direction of the arrows indicates the change from 2022 to 2024.

Indicator 2 (P1I2): Can women work at night in shops and commercial establishments?

Since 2022, four states have eased restrictions on women working at night in shops and commercial establishments.

- Of 23 states, 3 states continue to prevent women from working at night in shops and establishments.
- Of 23 states, 1 state allows women to work at night in only a few industries subject to permission.
- Of 23 states, 1 state allows women to work at night in only a few industries.
- Of 23 states, 1 state allows women to work in most industries subject to permission, allowing full freedom in others.
- Of 23 states, 16 now allow women to work in shops and establishments at night, subject to either certain conditions (12/23) or permission (4/23).
- Of 23 states, 1 state gives full freedom.

Figure 2: Women's freedom to work at night in shops and commercial establishments

*Direction of the arrows indicates the change from 2022 to 2024.

Indicator (P1I3): Can women work at night in plantations?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working at night in plantations.

- All 23 states continue to allow women to work at night in plantations subject to permission.

Figure 3: Women's freedom to work at night in plantations

Indicator 4 (P1I4): Can women contract workers work at night?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on contract women working at night.

- Of 23 states, 2 restrict women contract workers from working at night.
- Of 23 states, 7 allow women contract workers to work at night in only a few industries.
- Of 23 states, 1 state allows women contract workers to be employed at night in all industries subject to conditions.
- Of 23 states, 13 have imposed no restrictions on women contract workers from working at night.

Figure 4: Women contract workers' freedom to work at night

Indicator 5 (P1I5): Can women migrant workers work at night?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on migrant women working at night.

- Of 23 states, 21 restrict women migrant workers from working at night in most industries.
- Of 23 states, 2 allow women migrant workers to work at night.

Figure 5: Women migrant workers' freedom to work at night

Indicator 6 (P2I1): Can women work in jobs deemed hazardous in factories?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in jobs deemed hazardous in factories.

- All 23 states continue to restrict women from working in hazardous processes in factories.

Figure 6: Women's freedom to work in jobs deemed hazardous in factories

Indicator 7 (P2I2): Can women work in jobs deemed hazardous in shops and commercial establishments?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in jobs deemed hazardous in shops and commercial establishments.

- Of 23 states, 1 restricts women from participating in some hazardous processes in shops and establishments.
- Of 23 states, 22 allow women to participate in hazardous processes in shops and establishments.

Figure 7: Women’s freedom to work in jobs deemed hazardous in shops and commercial establishments

Indicator 8 (P2I3): Can women work in jobs deemed hazardous in plantations?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in jobs deemed hazardous in plantations .

- Of 23 states, 3 restrict women from participating in hazardous processes in plantations.
- Of 23 states, 20 allow women to participate in hazardous processes in plantations.

Figure 8: Women’s freedom to work in jobs deemed hazardous in plantations

Indicator 9 (P3I1): Can women work in jobs requiring lifting heavy objects?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in jobs requiring lifting heavy objects.

- Of 23 states, 21 restrict women from participating in tasks that require the lifting of heavy objects.
- Of 23 states, 2 allow women to participate in tasks that require lifting heavy objects, subject to permission.

Figure 9: Women's freedom to work in jobs requiring lifting heavy objects

Indicator 10 (P4I1): Can women work in country liquor establishments?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in country liquor establishments.

- Of 21 states, 11 restrict women from working in licensed country liquor establishments.¹
- Of 21 states, 3 allow women to work in licensed country liquor establishments subject to permission.
- Of 21 states, 7 have no restrictions on women working in country liquor establishments.

Figure 10: Women’s freedom to work in country liquor establishments

1. Of the 23 states studied, 2 states—Gujarat and Bihar—were excluded from indicator 10 because these states have banned the manufacture, sale, and purchase of alcohol.

Indicator 11 (P4I2): Can women work in foreign liquor establishments?

Since 2022, no state has changed its legal stance on women working in foreign liquor establishments.

- Of 21 states, 9 restrict women from working in licensed foreign liquor establishments.²
- Of 21 states, 12 allow women to work in licensed foreign liquor establishments either by granting permission (7/21) or placing no restriction at all (5/21).

Figure 11: Women’s freedom to work in foreign liquor establishments

2. Of the 23 states studied, 2 states—Gujarat and Bihar—were excluded from indicator 11 because these states have banned the manufacture, sale, and purchase of alcohol.

Conclusion

State governments across India are recognising the importance of encouraging women to enter the workforce. All states now have dedicated missions for women empowerment under 'Mission Shakti'. For instance, Uttar Pradesh has introduced the fifth phase of [Mission Shakti](#) aiming to empower women and foster their economic participation. At the Union level, the Government of India has recognised women's workforce participation as a key lever for the Viksit Bharat vision. The aim is to achieve 70% female workforce participation by 2047 (Press Information Bureau, 2025).

However, our regulations continue to prohibit women from entering the workforce or restrict their job opportunities. Prosperiti's State of Discrimination report 2025 finds very little change in legal barriers on female job seekers. India's 10 most populous states prohibit women from working in 217 different jobs in factories. These prohibitions or restrictions push women off the factory floor or increase the cost of hiring women. Research shows that sex-specific legal restrictions negatively correlate with female employment and make it difficult for women to transition into the formal sector (World Bank, 2018).

More recently, the Union and state governments have recognised the importance of deregulation in promoting growth and job creation. The Economic Survey 2024-25 observes that *"..Enhancing economic freedom for individuals and small businesses is arguably the most important policy priority to define and bolster India's medium-term growth prospect..."*. The Government of India has announced a High Level Committee for regulatory reforms to lead nationwide efforts to 'review all non-financial sector regulations, certifications, and licences' (Union Budget, 2025-26). To this end, Prosperiti's State of Discrimination report and datasets serve as a ready offering for states to remove restrictions on female jobseekers and 'deregulate' women's workforce participation. It is time to allow economic prosperity and agency for women and make them key drivers of our Viksit Bharat vision.

About us

Prosperiti (registered name: Eunomia Foundation) builds state capacity to increase economic freedom in India. Our mission is to lift a billion people into prosperity. We analyse state-level regulations, identify opportunities for reform, help build policy consensus, and assist partner states in implementation. Our knowledge products include State of Regulation reports, State of Discrimination reports, and bi-weekly analyses.

Our institutional partner

The Convergence Foundation (TCF) is an Indian philanthropic foundation committed to improving the lives of all Indians through rapid and sustained economic growth.

About The State of Discrimination Series

Each report in this series is a sub-national comparison of legal barriers to women's right to choose work in India. The reports compare states on the amount of economic freedom they offer to women job seekers. This edition of the State of Discrimination measures the change in legal discrimination against female job seekers across Indian states since 2022. For more information, please reach out to us info@prosperiti.org.in.